

Cloud Computing

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Question 1

Amazon Web Services (AWS) has provided several significant advantages to Ericsson. First of all, Ericsson has been able to manage its business due to the global infrastructure management services that are provided by AWS. This global infrastructure has enabled Ericsson to save the costs in various aspects of their business and thus, gain huge amount of profit (AWS, 2014). Moreover, due to the services of AWS, Ericsson is now able to develop and launch latest software and applications at any time according to the requirements of the market.

AWS has allowed Ericsson to increase and decrease their production according to the variation in demand. In addition, due to the remote access services provided by AWS, consumers of Ericsson can access the cloud based services irrespective of their location. Ericsson has also benefitted from AWS due to the cheap and scalable infrastructure platforms. The data centers of these infrastructures are located in all parts of the world (AWS, 2014). Likewise, the

Rightscale cloud management platform provided by AWS helped Ericsson substantially to dominate the market of cloud services.

Question 2

Amazon Elastic Compute Cloud which is more commonly known as EC2 is equipped with various distinguishing features. The most noteworthy feature is a complete environment consisting of memory, processor and software that is already configured. The scalability feature of EC2 can be availed instantly by simply paying for the service before using it. Thus, a lot of time is saved that can be otherwise wasted while buying and booting new server (Varia & Mathew, 2013). Moreover, the customers are required to pay according to the amount of service that they use. Also, the tools provided by EC2 can help preventing the occurrence of failure situations.

Amazon S3 provides storage service to the users of internet and it enables the developers to conveniently utilize the computing services based on the concept of web scaling. Thus, the users are now able to store and access vast amount of data without any constraints of time and location. Amazon S3 has helped to escalate the services of scaling for all the developers. Similarly, the flexibility feature of Amazon S3 also allows adding the desired functional layers (Varia & Mathew, 2013). Also, the customers are required to pay according to the amount of service that they use.

Rightscale allows easy deployment and management of various business applications covering all types of cloud networks. Precisely, Rightscale is used to create a link between the infrastructure of cloud and various applications. Furthermore, the users can manage and scale the complete deployment process of the server. The portability feature of Rightscale makes it quite

flexible and hence, it enables the organizations to run their business quite smoothly. In addition, testing and mitigating the risks associated with the applications are also its distinguishing features (Varia & Mathew, 2013).

Question 3

There are various security concerns associated with the cloud based services. First of all, all the confidential information of an organization can be accessed by the employees of the vendor company that provides the cloud services. In this regard, there are no specific rules and regulations that can commit the vendor company to conduct audits related to the data privacy. More so, location of data is another security concern as most of the times organizations are unaware about the location where the vendor company stores and manages the data of its users (A Vouk, 2008). In addition, in case of any disaster all the data of the users is lost and the vendor company does not take any responsibility for that loss.

Last, but not least, data theft is also a major concern that occurs most of the times due to lack of security barriers in the cloud network. As far as privacy of data is concerned, there should be certain rules and regulations which should bind the vendor company to ensure the privacy of data. Furthermore, layered security method should be adopted in order to ensure the protection of data and other associated assets (A Vouk, 2008). In this method usually five security levels are created that ensure network and physical security, detection of intrusion, management of firewall and encryption of data.

Question 4

Although there are numerous advantages of cloud computing, some possible issues associated with it can restrict its use. Among these issues, reliability can be a major issue which is sometimes difficult to maintain. This is due to the fact that the systems providing the cloud services may face down time problems and hence, interruption can occur in the services. In addition, a large amount of cost is involved in the development of applications which enable the transfer of data between the cloud network and the applications (A Vouk, 2008).

Likewise, the implementation of a secure cloud computing technology also requires a huge amount of investment. Also, the accessibility to the similar content by many users and scaling up and down ability of applications give rise to scalability issues. Nevertheless, this issue can be minimized by using the diagonal approach which is a combination of both horizontal and vertical scalability (Varia & Mathew, 2013). Furthermore, advancement in technology can help to reduce the costs involved in cloud computing technology. Also, proper maintenance and monitoring of systems can minimize the reliability issues.

References

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